

Artificial Intelligence and Human Intelligence: Analysis of Similarities and Differences

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Article information:

Manuscript received: 4 Aug 2024; **Accepted:** 4 Sep 2024; **Published:** 08 Oct 2024

Abstract: Artificial intelligence and human thinking are two different approaches to processing information and solving problems. Despite their significant differences in nature, artificial intelligence and human thinking have a number of similar characteristics. In this article, we will look at the main similarities and differences between artificial intelligence and human thinking based on an analysis of current research and sources.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, human thinking, information processing, learning, problem solving, the nature of intelligence, emotions, intuition, creativity, self-awareness.

In the modern world, artificial intelligence is rapidly developing and affecting various areas of human life. Despite its growing role, the question of similarities and differences between artificial intelligence and human thinking remains a hotly debated topic.

Both the human brain and artificial intelligence process data using complex algorithms and systems. Human thinking is based on neural connections formed through learning and experience. Similarly, artificial intelligence uses artificial neural networks trained on large amounts of data. According to researchers, "artificial intelligence and human cognition exhibit data processing processes such as pattern recognition and classification" [1]. These similarities allow AI to perform tasks previously considered the domain of human intelligence, such as medical diagnostics and natural language processing.

Both systems have the ability to learn. Human intelligence develops through experience and learning, which develops cognitive abilities and knowledge. Artificial intelligence, on the other hand, uses machine learning techniques that allow systems to analyze data and improve their functions based on experience. "The learning process in the human brain and artificial intelligence have similarities, such as adaptation and improvement based on new information and experience" [2]. This allows for continuous improvement of artificial intelligence systems and adaptation to changing conditions.

Both artificial intelligence and human intelligence are problem-solving oriented. The human brain uses cognitive strategies and logical reasoning to analyze situations and make decisions. Artificial intelligence is also designed to perform complex tasks by analyzing data and applying algorithms. "The ability of artificial intelligence to solve complex problems, such as strategic planning and process optimization, is similar to the human approach to problem solving" [3]. These similarities make artificial intelligence a valuable tool in a variety of industries, including industry, medicine, and government.

One of the main differences between artificial intelligence and human thinking is their nature. Human intelligence is biological and is based on the neural connections of the brain. On the other hand, AI is artificial and runs on software and hardware. "The human brain is biological in nature, and artificial intelligence is an artificial system created on the basis of computer technology" [4]. This difference

defines many aspects, including the capabilities and limitations of both systems.

Human thinking includes emotional and intuitive components that play an important role in making decisions and interacting with the world around us. Artificial intelligence, despite its abilities, does not have real feelings and intuition. "The emotional and intuitive aspects of human thinking are not available to artificial intelligence, which limits its ability to fully imitate the human mind" [5]. This difference makes artificial intelligence less capable of understanding and interpreting contexts related to human emotions and experiences.

Human intelligence is known for its ability to be creative, generate new ideas and innovative solutions. Artificial intelligence, despite its powerful computing power, primarily operates within predefined algorithms and programs. "The creative component of human thinking, which is related to the creation of unique and appropriate ideas, is not fully realized in artificial intelligence" [6]. This limitation of artificial intelligence emphasizes the importance of human intelligence in fields that require creativity.

Human thinking includes spiritual and moral thinking that guides behavior and decision-making. Artificial intelligence is programmable and can follow given moral algorithms, but has no moral beliefs of its own. "Ethical and spiritual aspects characteristic of human thinking cannot be completely recreated in artificial intelligence" [7]. This difference raises questions about the safety and responsibility of using artificial intelligence in critical tasks.

Human intelligence is characterized by self-awareness, that is, awareness of one's own existence and thinking. Artificial intelligence, despite its abilities, is not self-aware. "Self-awareness, the main feature of human intelligence, is absent in artificial intelligence, which limits its understanding of itself and the world around it" [8]. This difference emphasizes the uniqueness of the human mind and its ability to reflect.

Artificial intelligence and human intelligence are two phenomena that, despite their obvious differences, raise many questions about the nature of intelligence, consciousness, and the future of humanity.

The similarities between artificial intelligence and human intelligence can be explained as follows:

First, both types of intelligence are capable of learning and adapting to new circumstances. Humans learn from experience and AI learns from data.

Second, both AI and humans can solve problems ranging from simple arithmetic to complex abstract ones.

Third, both have the ability to analyze information, draw conclusions, and make decisions.

Fourth, both artificial intelligence and humans can recognize images, sounds, texts and other information.

Fifth, artificial intelligence is capable of generating new ideas and solutions, and humans have creative potential.

The differences between artificial intelligence and human intelligence can be described as follows:

- Human intelligence is the product of biological evolution, while artificial intelligence is the result of human engineering.
- Humans have self-awareness, emotions and subjective experience, which is not yet visible in artificial intelligence.
- Human creativity is often based on intuition, emotion and context, which is difficult to replicate in artificial intelligence.
- Human intelligence is related to the physical body and brain, while artificial intelligence exists in digital form.
- Human intelligence is limited by moral standards and ethical principles that artificial intelligence may not have.

In conclusion, there are similarities and differences between artificial intelligence and human thinking. Both systems have the ability to process information, learn, and solve problems, but differ in their nature, emotional and creative abilities, moral aspects, and self-awareness. Understanding these similarities and differences is important for the further development of artificial intelligence and its integration into society, as well as the recognition of the uniqueness of human intelligence.

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